

1 **Learning effectiveness of virtual environments for 3D terrain interpretation and data acquisition**

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3 **Abstract**

4 The aim of this study is to assess the effectiveness of different learning strategies for 3D terrain
5 interpretation and data acquisition by engineering students. According to the experimental design,
6 students received homogeneous training, followed by differential training, which divided the students into
7 three statistically homogeneous groups where each group was subject to a different learning process: 1)
8 serious video games learning; 2) learning using physical scale models; and 3) a theoretical class.
9 Afterwards, the students were evaluated using two tests under real field conditions. Results were obtained
10 for the following study variables: field-test scores and whether or not the student was repeating the
11 course. The students who learned using physical scale models obtained the best scores, significantly
12 higher than the scores of students using serious video games or a theoretical class among others
13 interesting results will be discussed in this paper. These findings open up new perspectives on the
14 teaching of surveying with respect to other teaching methods.

15 **Keywords:** Surveying, Learning, Data acquisition, Video games, Terrain interpretation

16 **Table of abbreviations**

DEM	Digital Elevation Model
RTK	Real Time Kinematic
CPS	Conventional Process Students
TPS	Tangible Process Students
VPS	Virtual Process Students

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19 **1. Introduction**

20 Surveying have undergone dramatic changes over the past 75 years in many countries as US (Frank
21 2006), Canada (McEwen 2006), Denmark (Enemark 2008), China (Song 2011), or New Zealand (Coutts
22 and Strack 2012). The introduction of new technologies, along with new surveying sciences has changed
23 the face of the surveying profession dramatically over this period (Frank, 2006). On the other hand, the
24 role of the surveyor remains relevant to the modern world, but there are notable changes in how surveyors
25 carry out their work and in the nature of that work (Young et al., 2012). This argues that changes are
26 needed associated educational programmes (Wang and Wang 2011; Coutts and Strack 2012).

27 Although there is a consensus on the instructional potential of serious games, there is still a lack of
28 methodologies and tools not only for design but also to support analysis and assessment (Arnab et al.
29 2015). Geospatial abilities of students are important from elementary school students (Wang et al. 2014)
30 but even more for engineering students. Field practice is an important part of training; however,
31 traditional teaching methods may not adequately manage, share and implement instruction resources and
32 thus may limit the instructor's ability to conduct field instruction (Wang et al. 2015). The objective of this
33 study is to assess the effectiveness of different learning strategies for 3D terrain interpretation and data
34 acquisition (Aguilera and Lahoz 2010) by engineering students.

35 As a ground survey technique, surveying is based on the determination and representation of the three-
36 dimensional position of objects on the Earth's surface or elements that are part of the Earth's surface but
37 were artificially created by humans, describing the geometric relationships between these objects in the
38 system generated (San-Antonio-Gomez et al. 2015). The virtualization of the real Earth's surface is
39 known as Digital Elevation Model (DEM) which generation requires a finite number of representative
40 points to be recorded from the surface. The most important points from two different types of points are
41 selected: breakline points and fill points. The first includes the points that describe a characteristic region
42 of the terrain. Generally, they occur where there are drastic changes in orientation or slope, known as
43 breaklines. These lines are divided into dividing lines, thalweg lines and lines where there is a change in
44 slope. Lines that define the tops and toes of slopes are of special interest as they almost exclusively
45 appear in anthropogenic terrain and are of great interest to engineering. Dividing lines separate two terrain

46 slopes, such as mountain ridges. A thalweg is the line where two slopes converge in the terrain, as in the
47 case of valleys or ravines. Top of slope lines are singular lines that define the changes in slope found at
48 the top of a slope, which are of considerable importance in civil engineering. The toe of the slope is
49 located at the bottom of the slope. This recording of the lines generates a more precise DEM and
50 decreases the number of fill points required. Therefore, a correct interpretation of the discretization of the
51 terrain is key. To do this, an engineer must decide the number of points or lines needed to provide a
52 correct description of the DEM.

53 The second type of element recorded is known as a fill point. Its function is to correctly describe the DEM
54 surface in smoother areas of the terrain. They are randomly selected and follow a constant density that
55 depends on the roughness or smoothness of the terrain. Fig. 1 shows a DEM generated using breaklines
56 and fill points.

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Fig. 1. 3D Model of a DEM generated using breaklines and fill points.

59 At the same time, the ability to discretize the terrain is conditioned by the actual intrinsic characteristics
60 of the surveying technique used. For example, a total station is less productive than a GPS/GNSS system
61 working in Real Time Kinematic (RTK) mode. In this sense, some studies have developed virtual
62 environments specifically designed to teach students how to use surveying equipment (Ellis et al. 2006)
63 (Dib and Adamo-Villani 2014) (Kuo et al. 2011). 3D terrain interpretation and its relation to data
64 acquisition methodologies is one of the most important points presented in this paper with respect to the
65 research cited above.

66 In order to obtain a good 3D definition of the terrain, students must be able to extrapolate their theoretical
67 knowledge of the representation of contour maps, clearly defining breaklines and fill points. At the same
68 time, the student must adjust data recording to the data acquisition methodology determined by the
69 surveying device. The student's success depends on how they combine these variables and manage real
70 scenarios in work conditions that may complicate their perception of the terrain. For example, terrain with
71 dense vegetation, trees or a developed area could lead a student to misinterpret the terrain and omit certain
72 representative elements when recording the data. The strengthening of the pairing of education and real
73 professional skills demanded in the work market is a rising tendency which has proven to successfully
74 prepare students for their professional life. Recently, several studies have focused on this aspect (Gider et
75 al. 2012) (Strong 2012). This research proposes three different teaching methods for 3D terrain
76 interpretation for the recording of topographic data. These teaching methods are differentiated by the
77 manner in which they present the same technical concept. The format used to explain a concept
78 (Megonigal et al. 2012) is decisive in this particular field of knowledge. The first method was based on a
79 classic theoretical class with multimedia content; specifically, slides, illustrations and chalkboard
80 drawings. The students subject to this process were referred to as Conventional Process Students (CPS).
81 This type of student merely observes the explanation. It has been demonstrated that these classical
82 teaching methodologies can be boring and lack student motivation (Martin-Gutierrez et al. 2013).

83 The second learning method combined a theoretical class with multimedia content and tangible elements
84 that could be used by the students, who were referred to as Tangible Process Students (TPS). An example
85 of this would be the use of scale models of the terrain surface to study the design of an irrigation system

86 on the land surface (Paz Gómez et al. 2004). It is important to highlight that models are frequently used in
87 the teaching of professional skills. Recent studies show the advantages of using models to teach other
88 branches of engineering such as irrigation control systems in agriculture (Molina et al. 2014), electronic
89 car parts (Albaladejo et al. 2013) or marine vehicles (Velasco et al. 2010).

90 The recent advances in software and computer technology have enabled the incorporation of dynamic
91 representations into a multitude of educational and training environments (Khacharem et al. 2015), so the
92 last learning method combined a theoretical class with a virtual interaction. These students were named
93 Virtual Process Students (VPS). Dragana Nikolić (Nikolić et al. 2011) stated that students perceive
94 simulation games to promote virtual interaction and generally make the class more interesting than
95 traditional methodologies.

96 Moreover, the students are significantly more motivated than they were prior to simulation. Therefore, the
97 objective of this study was to evaluate the ability to perform 3D terrain interpretation as the key to
98 developing engineering students' professional skills.

99 The research presented in this paper addresses the need to determine the effectiveness of the learning
100 processes for 3D terrain interpretation for the topographic recording of points, lines and surfaces by
101 engineering students. It is important to note that data acquisition from the Earth's surface primarily
102 depends on 3D terrain interpretation as represented by contour maps, and the theoretical knowledge of
103 topographic instruments and their use.

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105 **2. Experimental design**

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107 Three groups of students were evaluated, each trained with a different learning method. The first stage of
108 the experimental design consisted of a general theoretical class. In the second stage, each student group
109 performed 3D terrain interpretation and data recording using: 1) tangible physical models or scale models
110 (TPS); 2) serious video games of two different scenes (VPS); 3) students with no practical experience,
111 simulating students directly from a classical teaching method (CPS). The process included a third stage
112 that quantified the degree of skill achieved during 3D terrain interpretation with a real field evaluation.

113 The experiment was performed during the 2013/2014 academic year at the Higher Technical Engineering
114 School of the University of Seville (Spain). Sufficient students were selected to represent the student
115 group from a mid-size teaching institution. It is worth stating that the participating students were first time
116 surveying students as well as students repeating the course because they had not passed in previous years.
117 The number of students that participated in the study was determined by the sample size proposed by
118 Neyman-Pearson. The criterion chosen to define sample size was the comparison of the means of the
119 global scores for 3D terrain interpretation (breaklines and fill points) from the field tests performed. All 3
120 groups were compared using an all-pairwise multiple comparison procedure. The experimental units were
121 each student group, which were treated as independent variables. As will be later shown, 3D terrain
122 interpretation and data recording were evaluated for each student on a scale of 0 to 10 points. Therefore, it
123 was estimated that the calculation of the sample size of the mean overall score of a group was different
124 from another as long as the mean score of a study group was greater than or equal to $\Delta = 1.5$ points, that
125 is to say, a 15% difference in the mean score. Therefore, the initial hypotheses of the study were the
126 following (1):

$$\begin{aligned} 127 \quad & H_{01}: \mu_{CPS} = \mu_{TPS} \\ 128 \quad & H_{02}: \mu_{CPS} = \mu_{VPS} \\ 129 \quad & H_{03}: \mu_{TPS} = \mu_{VPS} \\ 130 \quad & H_{11}: \mu_{CPS} \neq \mu_{TPS} \\ 131 \quad & H_{12}: \mu_{CPS} \neq \mu_{VPS} \\ 132 \quad & H_{13}: \mu_{TPS} \neq \mu_{VPS} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

133 Where μ_{CPS} was the mean score of the CPS group, μ_{TPS} the mean score of the TPS group and μ_{VPS} the
134 mean score of the VPS group. As a result, the sample size of each group was determined using the
135 following expression (2):

$$136 \quad n = \frac{2\sigma^2(z_\alpha + z_\beta)^2}{\Delta^2} \quad (2)$$

137 In this study, the expected dispersion of the results obtained by the students was established with a
138 variance of $\sigma^2=2$ points. A conservative significance level for erroneous decisions, $\alpha=0.05$ and a strong

139 statistical power of $\beta=0.2$ were chosen. Equation (2) determined the number of students for each of the 3
140 groups to be $n=27.92\approx 28$ students, with the same value for each experimental unit ($n_{CPS}=n_{TPS}=n_{VPS}$). As a
141 result, the total number of students participating in the experiment was $N = 84$ students.

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143 **2.1. Stage 1: Theoretical class**

144 Stage 1 aimed to address four objectives. The first was to describe the initial knowledge of the students
145 selected for the teaching experience. The second objective was to homogenize the student sample to
146 theoretically prepare the students for development of the skill to be acquired. The next objective was to
147 verify that all of the students had obtained a sufficient level of knowledge to allow them to properly begin
148 the training. Lastly, experimental units were created from the scores obtained in the previous step,
149 ensuring that the student groups were both random and homogeneous and completely formed by a simple,
150 random selection.

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152 *2.1.1. Pre-lecture*

153 The questionnaire designed to assess students' previous knowledge of the subject was comprised of 6
154 questions of equal value: 1) concept of a breakline; 2) cross section of a slope; 3) cross section of a
155 divide; 4) cross section of a line where there was a change in slope; 5) cross section of the toe of a slope
156 and 6) cross section of the top of a slope. The possible final score for the questionnaire ranged from 0 to
157 10 points.

158 The questionnaire was designed to determine the theoretical concept of the different breaklines and, at the
159 same time, evaluate the students' spatial vision skills by having them graphically represent each of the
160 concepts. The questionnaire also aimed to evaluate the students at the start of the experiment and,
161 secondly, observe student homogeneity and preparation. It also prepared the students for the theoretical
162 class, highlighting some of the key concepts to be explained.

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164 *2.1.2. Theoretical lecture*

165 Next, a 15-minute basic theoretical class was taught to the students with the help of slides that graphically
166 illustrated the explanation. The following concepts were explained: definition of breaklines, definition of
167 DEM, interpretation of breaklines in examples represented with a contour map system/3D model and the
168 recording of data for DEM generation. It is worth noting that the data recording methodology was
169 demonstrated using a Leica Total Station TC 705, as is one of the more frequently used surveying
170 instruments in the surveying course taught at this university.

171 This theoretical content intended to homogenize the students' knowledge, conceptually preparing them to
172 understand what they were doing, why and how they should perform these tasks. This created a
173 foundation for the skills required for 3D terrain interpretation and data recording used to generate a DEM.

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175 *2.1.3. Post-lecture*

176 After the basic concept class, a new questionnaire was handed out to the students. The questions
177 coincided with those from the previous questionnaire. This questionnaire reevaluated the participants
178 from the teaching experiment with a score from 0 to 10 points. The comparison of the results from both
179 questionnaires was direct since they included the same questions and guaranteed that the students had
180 acquired the concepts required to complete the evaluation.

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182 *2.1.4. Creation of the experimental unit*

183 Once the students were scored using the above-mentioned questionnaire, they were sorted by score; for
184 example, from highest to lowest. The questionnaires were then separated into three groups, equally
185 dividing the scores into each of the groups. Consequently, three experimental units were obtained (CPS,
186 TPS and VPS), random and homogeneous in the distribution of scores, and therefore achieving statistical
187 robustness.

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189 **2.2. Stage 2: Practical learning**

190 The next stage centered on the use of teaching procedures directed toward developing the skills needed
191 for 3D terrain interpretation and the recording of topographic data in an independent and efficient way.

192 To do this, two of the three groups practiced interpreting and recording topographic data using two
193 different methods: interaction with physical scale models (TPS) and interaction with virtual models by
194 means of a serious video game (VPS). Both groups were allotted the same amount of practice time,
195 beginning and ending at the same time. The CPS group did not practice any skill in any way as it
196 simulated a traditional learning process for terrain interpretation for the recording of topographic data.

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198 *2.2.1. Scaled-terrain training*

199 Once the TPS group was formed, it was separated from the rest of the students to begin training. For this
200 purpose, three scale models were built to represent 3 scenes for the description of different types of terrain
201 orography. The scale model on the left of Fig. 2 shows orography typical of a quarry. One of its slopes
202 has characteristics that are typical of artificial human transformation of the land's surface while the other
203 slope represents a natural terrain, with average smoothing of the surface. The middle scale model
204 corresponds to a natural orography with a very mild change in slope. In this case, it is complicated for the
205 student to identify the breaklines, as it requires a more thorough analysis of the change in slope. Lastly,
206 the scale model on the right is a natural scene with more pronounced breaklines that were easier for the
207 student to identify.

208 The students could touch the scale model to enhance their experience during identification of the
209 breaklines. The TPS test time was 15 minutes, that is, 5 minutes for each model. This time was
210 determined in relation to the time that a student would spend attending a 60-minute theoretical surveying
211 class. Fig. 2 shows the configuration of the practice space where the scale models simulated data
212 recording with a total station.

213

214 Fig. 2. Configuration of the scene during scaled-terrain training with a Leica Total Station TC 705.

215 The scale models for the different terrains were hand-sculpted using polyester-reinforced fiberglass, and
216 painted to evoke the shadows produced by the sun in the shaded slopes as well as vegetation. The scaled
217 terrain models were 100 cm in length and 70 cm in width. Nonetheless, terrain models produced by 3D
218 printers could substitute these scale models. Initially, 3D printing should not achieve better results than
219 hand-sculpted fiberglass, as it provides conceptual schemes with a simplified structure for the teaching
220 objective. However, 3D printing could incorporate more detailed elements (trees, buildings, etc.), which
221 would be too difficult to incorporate with a hand-sculpted fiberglass model. Plus, there would be lower
222 manufacturing costs if the model was produced individually for the students, enabling scaled replicas of
223 real terrains to be produced for use in field practice, better preparing students for real measurements of
224 practice terrains.

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226 2.2.2. *Serious video game training*

227 The VPS group was taken to a computer lab (Fig. 3) for individualized practice interpreting the terrain
228 using two virtual immersions. Both virtual environments were composed of 3D models of two different
229 terrain surfaces whose texture was mapped using an orthophotograph. Specifically, one of the terrain
230 models selected corresponded to the scale model of a quarry (scale model on the left of Fig. 2). The same

231 quarry was chosen for the abovementioned teaching characteristics, but also because it would homogenize
232 the training of the TPS and VPS groups. The other scale model represented a real quarry known by the
233 name Burguillos. This model used the information recorded from the generation of a 10x10 m DEM
234 between the years 2010 and 2011 with a WMS server (IdeAndalucia 2014), and processed using TAO
235 Computer-Aided Surveying software (Perez-Romero, 2010). This quarry is an example of a real
236 engineering work scene, dedicated to the extraction of sand and gravel for construction; in particular, the
237 ore is used for obtaining artificial gravel and, part of the gangue is used as a sub-base material in the
238 construction of roads and highways. The models were treated with Autodesk 3Ds Max[®] Design 2014
239 software. In addition, these virtual environments did not include 3D vegetation models because they
240 would make the identification of the breaklines more difficult for the students who had greater difficulty
241 with space perception, making the tool less effective and therefore, reducing teaching efficacy.

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243 Fig. 3. VPS group during its virtual experience for the 3D interpretation and recording of topographic
244 data.

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246 Fig. 4. Serious video game for 3D interpretation of the Burguillos model where the breaklines are marked.

247 As a result, the video game provided individualized thematic exploration based on the users' interests.

248 The objective was to discover the breaklines after observation of and travelling over the land surface. For

249 this purpose, the user was placed far from the point to be found, marked by a moving arrow (Fig. 4) that

250 was not always visible from all points in the scene. To arrive at this point, the user of the serious video

251 game had to find a particular colored sign with the name of a type of breakline. By clicking on it,

252 breaklines would appear on the terrain in the same color as the sign that specified their type. With it, the

253 users could verify if what they had interpreted was correct or not. They could also continue exploring to

254 obtain different viewpoints of each of the correct terrain interpretations once all of the breaklines were

255 activated.

256 Several tools can be used to develop virtual environments, depending on the objectives pursued.

257 However, the objective of this serious video game was to fulfill E-Learning requisites, which has been

258 demonstrated to be a good alternative method for teaching spatial sciences (Manzano-Agugliaro et al.

259 2015). Accordingly, a visually attractive web video game format with few computer requirements was

260 chosen. Standard VRML language, recognized by the International Standardization Organization (ISO),

261 was used for this research, as the standard for the creation, distribution and representation of 3D elements
262 via Internet (ISO/IEC-14772-2 2004).

263 Once the virtual reality scenes were properly configured with respect to the browser, lighting, animation
264 and sensors, a web browser was selected for interaction with the scenes. There is a wide array of VRML
265 browsers, both members and non-members of the Web3D Consortium, however, the browser used for this
266 study was Cortona3D Viewer 7.0 run on Mozilla Firefox.

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268 **2.3. Stage 3: Student evaluation**

269 There are different methodologies for evaluating the skills acquired by students following a teaching
270 process. These on-line experiences may take into account a person's skill while others look for
271 comprehensive variables of engineering students' skills with the objective of establishing global standards
272 (Ball, et al. 2012) (Passow 2012).

273 The evaluation of skill in the 3D evaluation of terrain is performed by observing a limited surface, where
274 the student must identify two types of elements: breaklines and the number of points that define them.

275 Similarly, the evaluation of skill acquired by students using real environments (Yueh et al. 2012) is the
276 most recommended option for a correct experimental teaching design and was chosen for this study. After
277 observation, the students were to mark the breaklines on a photograph from their actual point of
278 observation. Fig. 5 shows two photographs of the points observed for both tests completed by the
279 students.

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281 Fig. 5. Photographs of two different surfaces showing the breaklines and points to be measured for their
 282 definition during student evaluation.

283 The figure above shows the solution for identification of the breaklines in both scenes and the topographic
 284 points recorded. Each breakline typology is identified with a different color. So the student can interpret
 285 the surface breakline easily thanks to the color. The tracing of these lines forms question 1 (Q1) for both
 286 tests. These lines were analyzed in 3 categories in function of their importance for definition of the DEM
 287 of the study area. The first category (main line) refers to the most important line for the definition of the
 288 DEM. At the same time, it is the most obvious line, and therefore should not go unnoticed by any of the
 289 students provided they have minimum knowledge of the subject. Each scene evaluated by the students

290 contained only one main line. The second category (relevant lines) included those lines that shape the
291 terrain in a less decisive manner. Their value was 75 % of the value of a main line. There were 4 relevant
292 lines in each case. Lastly, the recommendable lines were those lines that described part of the terrain to be
293 studied in detail. Their recording slightly improved the definition of the DEM. Each photograph contained
294 4 recommendable lines. Their value was 25 % of the value of a main line. In question 2 (Q2) of each test,
295 the student had to locate where they would record a point belonging to the previously identified breakline.
296 This evaluated their ability to apply their theoretical knowledge of the recording of points from a
297 surveying perspective with respect to density and relevance.

298 After all of the students from the teaching experience evaluated both scenes, 3 scores were given within
299 the following range of values: the minimum score was 0 points and the maximum score was 10 points.
300 The first score corresponded to identification of the breaklines (Q1), the second corresponded to the
301 identification of the points recorded (Q2) and the third was the arithmetic mean of both (Global Score,
302 GS).

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304 **3. Results and discussion**

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306 Once the total sample size and size of each experimental unit was established, the distribution of the
307 scores of N from the studies before and after the theoretical class was evaluated. Fig. 6 shows the
308 histograms of the scores achieved, ranging from 0 (minimum) to 10 (maximum) points.

Fig. 6. Histograms of the questionnaire scores before and after the theoretical class.

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The histogram of the scores before the theoretical class shows a distribution of scores throughout almost the entire established range. This brings us to believe that there were students with previous knowledge of the subject. This can be explained by the fact that there were students in the group who had repeated the course. It should be noted that the percentage of repeat students was: 21.4%, 32.1% and 28.3% for TPS, VPS and CPS respectively. These students' previous knowledge and the fact that basic aspects were included in the questionnaires allowed them to achieve a good score. Nevertheless, there was no significant statistical difference between the GS of first-time students and that of repeat students, with a P value of 0.91 using two-way ANOVA. This aspect seems contradictory at first. However, it shows how repeat students had never acquired profound knowledge of the subject and therefore, behaved in the same way as first-time students. As a consequence, the fact that a student had repeated the course did not explain any variation in the results of the teaching experience.

322 In spite of this, the mean score of the first questionnaire was 2.57 points ($\sigma=2.42$ points). This value
323 indicates that despite the wide distribution of scores, all of the students showed little previous knowledge
324 of the key concepts covered in the theoretical class.

325 With respect to the results shown in the post-theoretical class histogram, all of the students achieved a
326 minimum score of 5 points. Students with scores higher than 5 were considered theoretically prepared to
327 begin skill evaluation or topographically interpret the terrain. The mean value of the distribution was 8.81
328 points ($\sigma=1.1$ points). One aspect worth highlighting about this value is that on average the students
329 correctly assimilated the information explained in the theoretical class. This was confirmed with a
330 Wilcoxon signed-rank test, comparing the scores before and after the theoretical class, where the data did
331 not adjust to a normal distribution. The result from the test suggests that there are statistical differences
332 showing a high significance ($P<0.001$). Because all of the students passed the initial test, the theoretical
333 class was considered successful, and ensured that the students could perform the test from a theoretical
334 standpoint.

335 Stage 3 of the experimental design was based on the scores from Q1, Q2 and the GS from both tests,
336 which differed in the location of the terrains. In addition to distinguishing each student by group (TPS,
337 VPS and CPS), it was recorded whether or not the students were repeating the course. After the teachers
338 scored each test, the distribution of the scores achieved for each test by the students from each group and
339 the arithmetic mean of both were determined as shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Scores for Test 1, Test 2 and Global Scores for each of the experimental units.

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In a first observation, a homogeneous behavior was qualitatively observed in each of the experimental units. This aspect was important for detecting any differences in the tests with respect to the level of difficulty for terrain interpretation or any variables that may have caused a differential behavior in the students' responses in either of the tests. With this objective in mind, a Pearson correlation was performed between the scores for test 1 and test 2 for each of the 3 student groups (Table 1).

A high correlation was observed between test 1 and test 2 in the TPS and VPS groups ($r_{TPS}=0.871^{***}$ and $r_{VPS}=0.787^{***}$). For CPS, this correlation was normal with $r_{CPS}=0.444^{**}$. Furthermore, if the mean scores of each test are compared within each student group, it can be concluded that there were no differences in any of the cases given that the T-Student test for the TPS and CPS groups presented the following values: $P_{TPS}=0.544$ y $P_{CPS}=0.86$. Since the VPS group did not adjust to a normal distribution, a Mann-Whitney rank sum test was performed with $P_{VPS}=0.974$. It was statistically proven that the tests were performed in a way that did not introduce outliers or any other kind of alterations in the data for students within the same experimental unit, therefore validating the evaluation.

356 Table 1. Pearson correlation for the test results for the TPS, CPS and VPS groups.

	Test 2 TPS	Test 1 VPS	Test 2 VPS	Test 1 CPS	Test 2 CPS
Test 1 TPS	0.871***	-0.229	-0.226	0.115	0.255
Test 2 TPS		-0.196	-0.122	0.082	0.155
Test 1 VPS			0.787***	0.075	-0.249
Test 2 VPS				-0.068	-0.227
Test 1 CPS					0.444**

357 $P^{***}<0.001$, $P^{**}<0.05$, the rest of the values are not statistically significant.

358 By studying the behavior of test 1 with respect to test 1 for each of the other experimental units, a very
 359 low correlation with low r values was observed. This comparison of the scores from test 1 with respect to
 360 each of the student groups also showed a low statistical significance of any relationship between them.
 361 Test 2 showed similar behavior in magnitude to test 1 and any relationship with test 2 can be ruled out by
 362 comparing the scores to those from the other student groups. As a result, this confirms that each training
 363 process was different from the others from an evaluation viewpoint. This implies a different behavior for
 364 each experimental unit with respect to the others when evaluating 3D terrain interpretation skill using
 365 topographic concepts. Therefore, the abovementioned training processes showed statistically different
 366 evaluations, an aspect that strengthens the experiment since it is able to compare independent groups.
 367 This was confirmed by performing a one-way ANOVA on the GS for the TPS, VPS and CPS groups. A
 368 large difference was found between the student groups with a P value of 0.002**. A pairwise multiple
 369 comparison procedure between the three experimental units (Table 2), showed how TPS differed
 370 significantly from VPS and CPS. However, there was not enough statistical difference to state that VPS
 371 and CPS showed differences with respect to their means. This scenario is far from what would be
 372 expected prior to data analysis, as TPS and VPS should have obtained better results than CPS due to the
 373 simple fact that they involved some kind practice.

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375 Table 2. All-pairwise multiple comparison procedures according to the global result for both tests and the
 376 first and second questions of the tests.

	Comparison	Diff of means
GS ¹	TPS vs. CPS	1.614**
	TPS vs. VPS	1.279**
	VPS vs. CPS	0.335
Q1 ¹	TPS vs. VPS	1.259***
	TPS vs. CPS	1.201***
	VPS vs. CPS	0.058
Q2 ²	TPS vs. CPS	16.271**
	TPS vs. VPS	10.036
	VPS vs. CPS	6.235

377 ¹Holm-Sidak method. ²Dunn's method. Values of significance: P***<0.001 and P**<0.05.

378 Another point worth emphasizing is that the use of serious video games (VPS) did not improve either of
 379 the two skills studied in this article with respect to CPS. Significant improvements were observed in
 380 students from other studies when another type of virtual scene was used however, they did not
 381 contemplate the use of video games during the teaching of a course (Thomas et al. 2013). However, as
 382 described by Ebner and Holzinger, the use of serious video games in the teaching of Civil Engineering
 383 does not improve the learning of students trained solely with a classical procedure (Ebner et al. 2007). Is
 384 important to cite that other studies also reach similar conclusions related to digital technologies, where
 385 for learning nor has generation had a radical impact on learning characteristics of higher
 386 education students (Lai and Hong 2015).

387

388 This aspect reconfirms the research presented in this paper. On the other hand, other variables may have
 389 influenced this experimental design, reducing teaching efficiency when serious video games are used
 390 since it has been shown that the use of technology in educational centers is not always successful

391 (Wentworth and Middleton 2014). For example, lack of skill using the serious video game, as a result of
392 inadequate experience with virtual reality or for other reasons, such as simplified virtual models (Lee et
393 al. 2015), could decrease students' conviction of the concept they are practicing. It is also possible that
394 integration of the serious video game was not properly implemented in the teaching process. The video
395 game was integrated in function of the students' characteristics, the knowledge they should acquire and
396 their participation in the serious video game (Busby et al. 2000). Hsu showed video games are
397 successfully integrated when the faculty has experience in the use of these virtual tools (Hsu 2010). This
398 is the case of the faculty that conducted this research, which allows us to dismiss this assumption. As a
399 result, only TPS was better than a classical class under these study conditions.

400 On the other hand, Q1 of the test was related to the geometric interpretation and spatial vision of the
401 student. This question, statistically-speaking, showed differences again between the three groups with a
402 high level of significance ($P^{***}<0.001$). When comparing the groups between themselves, TPS differed
403 from VPS and CPS with a high level of significance, which, at the same time, showed no differences
404 between them. However, this tendency was broken when Q2 of the tests was analyzed. In this case, the
405 variability of the difference of the means was disproportional with respect to the first question. Statistical
406 differences were only found between TPS and CPS; no differences could be found between TPS and VPS
407 or VPS and CPS. The explanation of this phenomenon lies in the nature of the question. The second
408 question attempted to place a value on the students' topographic knowledge based on previous 3D terrain
409 interpretation. Fig. 8 shows the behavior described above for the scores for Q1 and Q2 in each of the
410 experimental units: TPS, VPS and CPS.

411

412 Fig. 8. Mean score of first (Q1) and second questions (Q2) for both tests and each experimental unit.

413 Fig. 8 shows the students' best response to Q1. In fact, TPS obtained a good score for Q1 with a mean
 414 value of 6.09 points ($\sigma=1.383$ points). Both VPS and CPS had a very close mean value of 5 for this same
 415 question, which was considered the minimum level, with mean values of 4.83 points ($\sigma=1.07$ points) and
 416 4.89 points ($\sigma=1.35$ points) respectively. According to the previously analyzed data and taking into
 417 account Fig. 8, it can be stated that only TPS students were able to successfully develop the skill for 3D
 418 terrain interpretation, greatly differing from VPS and CPS. These groups did not achieve the minimum
 419 desirable level but were very close.

420 None of the groups surpassed the minimum threshold value of 5 points for Q2. TPS presented a mean
 421 value of 4.44 points ($\sigma=3.1$ points), 3.15 points ($\sigma=3.05$ points) for VPS and 2.42 points ($\sigma=2.43$ points)
 422 for CPS. This is because this skill could not be evaluated during the students' initial learning stage in a
 423 surveying course, as was the case in this study. From this statement, one could assume that 3D terrain
 424 interpretation alone is not sufficient for a student to be capable of using topographic equipment and
 425 acquiring the points needed for the correct geometric description of a DEM. However, the development of
 426 skill in 3D terrain interpretation alone did facilitate topographic skill in the selection of points. In fact, the
 427 TPS students were able to situate themselves very close to the minimum level of 5 points. VPS and CPS

428 were in proportion to Q1, whose topographic skills were strengthened because of 3D terrain
429 interpretation.

430

431 **4. Conclusions**

432

433 This study shows how engineering students were trained for 3D terrain interpretation and acquisition of
434 topographic data for the generation of a digital elevation model by means of three teaching procedures: 1)
435 practice with tangible elements (scale models of the terrain); 2) intangible elements (serious video game
436 for terrain exploration); and 3) no training (students performed the test exclusively with theoretical
437 knowledge). Contrary to initial predictions, only the tangible process student group passed the evaluation
438 with a score greater than 5 points (considered the minimum desirable score), and was statistically
439 different from the rest of the experimental units. The virtual process student and conventional process
440 student groups did not show statistical differences and were unable to pass the evaluation of the skill
441 analyzed. As a result, the evaluation of 3D terrain interpretation was successful from a scoring viewpoint.
442 In this sense, students improve their terrain surface interpretation skills when tangible elements are used
443 in class which implementation is recommendable in engineering student curriculums on survey subjects.
444 On the other hand, this research was only partially successful with respect to the scores for the recording
445 of points with topographic devices for the generation of a digital elevation model. Further work must be
446 performed in order to evaluate this surveying skill. However, it shows how 3D terrain interpretation
447 greatly influences the recording of topographic data, achieving scores of close to 5 points, a threshold
448 above which the evaluation was considered successful. Future research will focus on studying the
449 appropriate combination of these learning processes, since the authors consider a correct combination of
450 these processes to be the key to improving the teaching of surveying.

451

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453

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459

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